

The Computer Replacement Program for the Joint Surveillance Target Attack Radar System¹

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Abstract—This paper presents development and testing results of the Computer Replacement Program (CRP) for the Joint Surveillance Target Attack Radar System (Joint STARS). Joint STARS, which consists of a modified Boeing 707-300 (E-8C) developed by Northrop Grumman and Common Ground Stations developed by Motorola, provides theater commanders near real-time surveillance and attack support information on moving and stationary targets. Diminishing manufacturing sources and an emphasis on life-cycle cost reduction required a modernization program that took maximum advantage of commercial equipment. The primary program objectives were maximizing marketplace support, reducing life-cycle costs and facilitating cyclic upgrades. CRP implemented this via a commercial off-the-shelf-based open architecture. The Computer Replacement Program met all its development objectives and will be fielded on the entire 15-aircraft Joint STARS fleet. Lessons learned included applying innovative acquisition processes in an open architecture, adapting to processes while under schedule pressure, ensuring early operational tester involvement, and estimating laboratory and ground testing in addition to flight-testing. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not represent views of the U.S. government or their contractors.

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I. NOMENCLATURE

ASCIET	All Service Combat Identification Evaluation Team
BIT	Built-in Test
CGS	Common Ground Station
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CRP	Computer Replacement Program
DT/OT	Development Test / Operational Test
EMI	electromagnetic interference
FDDI	fiber distributed data interface
FTI	fixed target indicator
IEEE	Institute of Electrical & Electronics Engineers
IQT	informal qualification test
JTIDS	Joint Tactical Information Distribution System
LAN	local area network
MTI	moving target indicator
O&C	operations and control
PSP	programmable signal processor
RAID	redundant array of independent disks
RASP	radar airborne signal processor
SAR	synthetic aperture radar
SCDL	surveillance and control data link
SEM	system environmental manager
STARS	Surveillance Target Attack Radar System
TADIL	Tactical Digital Information Link
TSPI	time space position information
VMS	virtual memory system

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2. INTRODUCTION

Diminishing manufacturing sources and reduced budgets have challenged the acquisition community to create new ways of developing and supporting weapon systems. Use of commercial equipment has been encouraged as a means to reduce the impact of these challenges. The advantages of commercial equipment include faster development, use of best commercial practices, ability to leverage commercial investment & new technology, and reduced costs.

However, use of commercial equipment can be challenging for many reasons including:

- Frequent change of commercial products.
- Built-in assumptions of end-user processes that may not match military processes.
- Products driven by marketplace instead of the weapon system.
- Licensing, data rights, and warranties.
- Limited control of releases.
- Limited visibility into source code.
- Different architectures across system components.
- Dependencies among system components.

To help mitigate the risk of using commercial equipment, weapon system managers must evolve systems continuously. This is accomplished by anticipating continuous change, relying on iterative development and sustainment processes, and evaluating mission needs, product updates, and technology advances continuously. Acquisition personnel can make a long-term commitment to commercial-based systems with flexible contract vehicles and long-term relationships in the community [1]. A key program office challenge is to sustain fiscal resources to fund for this continual evolution beyond completion of the initial design.

Reducing system life cycle costs was a major goal of the program. Future equipment replacements were anticipated to upgrade system components and thereby address performance improvements and obsolescence over the life of the program. In order to meet this goal, the Joint STARS Computer Replacement Program designers provided a flexible system architecture using industry standard racks, cable troughs and cooling, standard computer interfaces, protocols and network architecture to maximize current and future marketplace support.

Reduced budgets have also produced a rise in combined Developmental Test/Operational Test (DT/OT). Department of Defense Manual 5000.2R stresses using combined DT/OT to the greatest extent possible [2]. The CRP ran OT concurrently with system level performance verification (DT). Combined DT/OT provided early feedback on the operational effectiveness and suitability of the modified E-8C system. In addition to combined DT/OT, two dedicated OT sorties were flown at the end of the program.

This paper provides a description of the Joint STARS system and its computer replacement program. Themes include acquisition processes for open architecture systems, use and packaging of commercial equipment, software development and baseline innovations, combined DT/OT, and system testing using a variety of venues (software integration laboratory, hardware-in-the-loop facility, and a test aircraft—both ground testing and flight testing). As with any program, “lessons learned” are discussed. Finally, conclusions are provided.

3. PROGRAM DESCRIPTION

Joint STARS Description

Joint STARS provides theater commanders near real-time surveillance and attack support information on moving and stationary targets. Joint STARS consists of an E-8C developed by Northrop Grumman and Common Ground Stations (CGSs) developed by Motorola. Figure 1 shows the E-8C and the CGS.

Figure 1 E-8C Aircraft and Common Ground Station

The E-8C is a Boeing 707-300 series aircraft modified with a multi-mode radar, operations & control (O&C) equipment, communications equipment, and data-link equipment. The multi-mode radar subsystem features a side-looking,

phased-array radar operating at X-band, electronically steered in azimuth and mechanically steered in elevation. Wide area surveillance moving target indicator (MTI) is the primary radar mode. The radar interleaves the MTI mode with synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and fixed target indicator (FTI) imagery. The O&C subsystem is the mission equipment and user interface through 18 operator workstations. Operators develop radar service requests to dynamically schedule radar modes. They monitor system operations and control display of radar information with cartographic, hypsographic, and order-of-battle databases. The O&C also predicts areas screened from the radar's field of view, provides automatic tracking of targets, and replays radar history data. The communications subsystem provides secure, jam-resistant UHF communications plus secure VHF and HF voice communications. The data-link subsystem uses the Surveillance and Control Data Link (SCDL), a secure, jam-resistant Ku-band digital data link, to broadcast multi-mode radar data and exchange command and control information with CGs. The E-8C also uses the Joint Tactical Information Distribution System (JTIDS), a secure, jam-resistant L-band data link, to exchange information with other JTIDS equipped platforms.

Computer Replacement Program (CRP) Description

Hardware—The existing E-8C operations and control subsystem which was comprised of a MIL-VAX based five-computer architecture (and an additional four radar programmable signal processors [PSPs]) was upgraded by the CRP. The CRP replaced that existing architecture with a

simpler, dual computer architecture based on commercial processors. The CRP architecture comprises two central computers and two "Radar Airborne Signal Processor" (RASP) computers, both types configured as "one active and one redundant back-up". Figure 2 provides a system level illustration of the CRP modifications.

Figure 2 CRP Modifications

Figure 3 illustrates the CRP data rack configuration. A major consideration in the design of the data racks was accommodating the commercial equipment within the airborne environment. Two major factors related to this environment were shock & vibration and electromagnetic interference (EMI). Commercial equipment is typically designed to meet a standard office environment, not that of a

Figure 3 CRP Data Racks

military aircraft. To maintain maximum flexibility for future upgrades and minimize the cost of the racks, shock & vibration and EMI were considered at the rack level and not the "box" level. Vibration/shock dampers were employed to protect the equipment from airborne vibration and shock. "Crash loading" was addressed by designing the racks to restrain the equipment during that condition and provide safety to the operators. The metal racks employed EMI door filters & gaskets as well as shielded "rack-to-rack" cable troughs to provide 60 dBi isolation and thereby provided the required attenuation to address radiated emissions. A draw-through cooling system was implemented in both the data racks and the operator workstation consoles to address the convection cooling requirements of the commercial equipment. Cabin air entered the front of racks through removable air filters. This air was pulled through the racks by "Line Replaceable Unit" internal fans and exhausted out the rear through adjustable exhaust vents. A portion of the exhaust air was drawn into the forward cargo bay or overboard using an exhaust fan and ducting. The remaining portion of the exhaust air was mixed with Environmental Control System cooling air as it discharged into the main cabin. Data Rack 16 used ambient cooling.

The central computer mass storage device, which is an array of disks with removable disk modules, dramatically increased disk storage from the previous design by utilizing current 9 GByte drives to replace the existing 1 GByte drives. Already, 36 GByte drives are being planned to replace the 9 GByte baseline for the fielded system. Additionally, CRP replaced the following equipment within the existing 18 operator workstations: commercial computers replace the existing militarized processors. Three-bay mass storage devices and removable disk modules (interchangeable with the central computer mass storage device) replace the embedded disks and removable transportable disk modules. Finally, the keyboards, mouse and display were replaced by commercial devices. Figure 4 illustrates the operator workstation.

A switched fiber optic distributed data interface (FDDI) in a "star" configuration using a local area network (LAN) hub that employs "cross-bar switch" technology, replaces the copper, "dual-ring", 10baseT Ethernet operator workstation LAN. Industry standard input-output cards in a separate Versa Module Eurocard chassis, an external Global Positioning System clock card and two Digital Audio Bus Interfaces, mounted in the Communication Rack replace the Joint STARS Communications card functionality. A serial data hub, known as a Local Area Transport Server, provides "low-level" signal/interface access to enhance maintenance capability on the aircraft. A LAN Bridge provides Ethernet to FDDI connectivity required to connect subsystems, not modified by CRP, to the central computers.

Figure 4 Operator Workstation

Software—The CRP software development team merged the existing Joint STARS software baseline with the software modifications required to re-host on Alpha-based computers. To create a new "Single Software Baseline" (SSB), unique features of the existing Ground Support System were included in the merge, thus making it possible to build a system disk from the SSB that provides the Joint STARS CRP system environment in both the aircraft and ground-based support and training systems. This is a breakthrough in Joint STARS software sustainment enabling software changes to be made simultaneously in both aircraft and ground systems.

The re-host and functionality merge process migrated software to the target environment in major functional groups: Communications, System Health, Executive Services, Radar Management, and System Recovery. This spiral migration effort featured the cooperative teaming of software programming staff with seasoned test personnel, leveraging existing formal test procedures as a resource for creating a new baseline of Informal Qualification Test (IQT) procedures. The format and style of these new IQTs enabled their productive reuse over several levels of system integration. The expanded test case content of the new IQT procedures was directly responsible for the detection and correction of over 50 problems that were legacy from the previous software baseline.

CRP designers incorporated a number of features to enhance code portability. The Virtual Memory System operating system reduces dependencies and enhances the portability of code between computing systems (e.g., Windows NT). FORTRAN-77, which was originally used for all non-system environmental manager (SEM) software, was retained for slightly modified SEM processes along with all new CRP mandated non-SEM software. The C computer language was used for all new SEM processes. Mixing of C and FORTRAN in the same process on a unit-by-unit basis was avoided, as this significantly increases the complexity of the code and reduces its portability. Changes to man-machine interface code were limited to tabular display modifications required to support architecture changes in central processing unit configuration. The designers used Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) standard floating point processing for compatibility with other operating systems. The display software was switched from the vendor specific Programmer's Hierarchical Interactive Graphics System to Open Graphics Library, a vendor-neutral software interface which was the optimum environment for development of interactive graphic applications.

As with the central computer, one RASP assumes the functions of the four previous PSPs while the second RASP is used as an on-line spare. The functions performed by the previous radar pulse compression unit and signal preprocessor were also incorporated into the RASP's software. These changes significantly simplify the radar processing chain hardware, thereby improving reliability and reducing weight and power consumption. The PSP micro code, originally written in FORTRAN, was rewritten in C for the MTI, the SAR/FTI and the antenna scan pattern signal processing functions. The radar data processor MTI association process software was also written in C. Additionally, the pulse compression unit and signal preprocessor functions, which were originally developed based on simulation algorithms, were written in C. Software to control RASP data capture was also developed for Redundant Array of Independent Disk (RAID) recording for use on the test aircraft. Finally, new software was written in C to manage the RASP reconfiguration (i.e. failover) function.

Test Conduct—The Joint STARS Program Office at Hansom Air Force Base, Northrop Grumman, and the Joint STARS Test Force co-located with Northrop Grumman in Melbourne, FL became an Integrated Product Team. Facilities included a software integration laboratory, hardware-in-the-loop facility, and a test aircraft (E-8C tail number 90-0175). The test aircraft was fully production representative. The members of this team participated in all of the major CRP procurement meetings leading up to the final CRP design. CRP system test occurred in three phases from September 1999 through March 2000. The first phase involved development and integration testing in Northrop Grumman's Integrated Test Facility and on the test aircraft.

The second phase involved system level performance verification to ensure that the CRP architecture met or exceeded the Joint STARS System Specification. A subset of historical system-level test points was chosen since CRP did not change the system functionality. For CRP-unique features, the team developed new test points and procedures. The third phase involved combined DT/OT and, for the most part, ran concurrently with system level performance verification. Combined DT/OT provided early feedback on the operational effectiveness and suitability of the E-8C system. Two dedicated OT sorties were flown — one supported a fighter data link test and the other supported the All-Service Combat Identification and Evaluation Team (ASCIET) exercise. In all, 16 sorties for over 125 hours were flown.

Instrumentation, Tools, and Recording—The following instrumentation, tools, and recording devices were used:

- Time space position information (TSPI) units were used on ground targets as truth data for the E-8C radar data. The TSPI equipment provided latitude/longitude location verification of each moving vehicle used during testing and used the differential version of the Global Positioning System.
- A Digital Cassette Recording System incremental was used to record the various databus signals (radar subsystem bus, JTIDS data bus, digital data bus).
- The RASP RAID recording system was used to record data from the FDDI LAN as well as high-density radar In-phase and Quadrature (I&Q) data.
- The Mission History Data File and Mission Archive File were used to record various system messages.
- The Electronic Target Simulator and the Mobile Electronic Target Simulator were used as calibrated electronic targets during various radar tests.
- The Navigation System Emulator test tool, Version 3.5, provided navigation data to the laboratory.
- The SCDL Signal Injector Monitor test tool, Version 2.0, simulated the entire SCDL link and was used to create a load on the digital data bus.
- The JTIDS Test Device, Version 2.1, was used to generate messages on the JTIDS data bus.
- The Junction Box Stimulator was a piece of laboratory test equipment used to generate discrete system signals in the laboratory.
- The automatically recorded Fault Alert Error File was printed and used during data analysis.
- The Radar Airborne Signal Processor Simulator, Version 1.0, was used to create a load on the digital data bus and during testing of the radar system noise performance monitoring parameter.
- Various minor test tools such as a stop watch, a communications test set, a serial bus analyzer, a stand alone control panel, radio frequency noise sources, jammers, and breakout boxes were used.

4. RESULTS

The CRP performance evaluation criteria were simple—perform as well as the previous Follow-on Full Scale Development, five-computer system. Therefore, the test program primarily involved regression testing. Most objectives involved demonstrating that the system did not degrade performance. There were no new specifications for improved performance; however, the team expected the new system to provide an increase. The comprehensive test program embraced the following areas:

- Voice Communication
- Navigation
- System Initialization
- Equipment Failover
- TADIL-J Upgrade
- Built-in Test (BIT) Management
- Performance Monitoring
- SCDL
- Automatic Tracking
- Contingency Enhancements Backward Compatibility
- Radar Multi-Mode
- Radar Management
- Radar Performance
- Operational Environment

The CRP modification met all test objectives with a few minor discrepancies. Performance improvements were noted in numerous areas.

Voice Communication—The digital audio bus interface coupled with the new computer architecture provided significant improvement to the voice communication control system stability. The entire system appeared more robust with updates to displays occurring quicker. Communication-Plan-of-the-Day downloads took only 45 seconds compared to 60 seconds previously.

Navigation—The CRP modification did not degrade navigation performance. Test engineers successfully demonstrated the Navigation/Flight Management System's ability to automatically exchange flight plans and Mission Flight Patterns between the flight crew and the mission crew. Testers also successfully demonstrated the ability to provide and distribute required equipment monitoring, flight monitoring, planning information (including waypoints, flight plans, and mission pattern information) and navigation equipment advisories to the mission equipment and flight crew. The navigator successfully demonstrated the E-8C flight path planning and monitoring capabilities. Testers also successfully performed a reinitialized air alignment, in addition to a non-reinitialized air alignment. In both cases, the inertial navigation unit accepted position and velocity corrections and the inertial navigation unit drift errors decreased toward zero, as expected.

System Initialization—Testers observed no degradation in area initialization or transition functionality. The capability to transition between mission, non-mission, & flight modes, transfer to a new mission area, set the system time-of-day, control communication & datalink databases, and functional equivalence of all workstations were demonstrated. Additionally, the CRP modification provided considerable timesavings for distributions of and transitions to new mission centers as compared to the previous configuration.

Equipment Failover—The new CRP architecture improved the failure containment and recovery time in several areas by replacing the Joint STARS communication card with the independent digital audio bus interface and consolidating the system monitoring & control, central data processing, and radar data processor functionality into a single central computer. The 3-5 minute general-purpose computer reconfiguration of the previous configuration was replaced with a 15-25 second central computer failover.

TADIL-J Upgrade—Testers evaluated a subset of the TADIL-J capabilities in flight and in the laboratory. These capabilities (emergency points, tracks, change data orders, data update requests, SCDL platform location, and air-to-ground environment/category) were not affected by the CRP architecture.

Built-in Test (BIT) Management—Testers demonstrated the following BIT management capabilities:

- Automatically run operational readiness tests to the line-replacement-unit level and correctly report BIT status to the operators at any workstation.
- The printer served as a mechanical indication of BIT faults for the system. Additionally, this test verified on-line BIT was executed at periodic intervals.
- Report and display radar antenna phase shifter failures. In addition, this test demonstrated the capability to report BIT fault detections, including radar BIT fault detection reports and periodic mission equipment status to the SCDL.
- Operators could manually initiate diagnostics on selected computer program accessible mission equipment, datalink and navigation group equipment simultaneously and independently via any workstation when the system was initialized for either Flight Operations or Mission Operations.

Performance Monitoring—Testers demonstrated the capability to monitor workstation, data bus, LAN, central computer and navigation performance during Flight Operations and Mission Operations. Alerts were displayed at selected workstations when the values of the appropriate performance monitoring parameters exceeded preset adaptable thresholds. Radar performance, including radar antenna phase shifter temperatures, was successfully monitored. Testers also demonstrated the capability to display system equipment status on a single page while in

Flight Operations and Mission Operations. Finally, testers demonstrated the capability to monitor performance-monitoring data simultaneously and independently during Flight Operations and Mission Operations.

SCDL—All uplink text messages and radar service requests were received error free. There was no evidence of SCDL bus stoppages or loss of aircraft location data. Additionally, SCDL regression testing used a CGS with no errors.

Automatic Tracking—Testers demonstrated the following A-Track capabilities:

- Route-constrained and unconstrained A-Tracks on targets with varying speeds were continuous.
- The automatic tracking function provided continuous tracking for targets in route-constrained and unconstrained cases where the targets were halted for less than and greater than the MTI correlation timeout setting.
- Arbitrary-constrained and unconstrained A-Tracks provided continuous tracking on targets undergoing turns.
- The automatic tracking function provided the capability to predict an A-Track's centroid position for vehicle groups traveling at low speed (constrained and unconstrained tracks).

Contingency Enhancements Backward Compatibility—CRP modifications did not have any negative impacts to operation of the SATCOM initial capability package performance. Conversely, the SATCOM Package did not affect operation of the E-8C systems when the test team removed or powered off the equipment.

Radar Multi-Mode—Performance improvements occurred in the following areas:

- Shorter surveillance times for interleaved SAR.
- Lower probability of false returns for ground referenced coverage areas and attack control areas.
- Smaller circular error probability for MTI, SAR and FTI.

Radar Management—The CRP radar management functions performed similar to those tested during Follow-on Full Scale Development. The system provided a robust radar management capability and was able to successfully meet mission requirements.

Radar Performance—All radar laboratory performance results met or exceeded the results obtained during Follow-on Full Scale Development. Testers verified that jammer strobe/azimuth detection, threshold, resolution, accuracy and reporting successfully met the System Specification and that operator's displays contained correct information.

Operational Environment—The following 12 effectiveness and 4 suitability measures of performance were evaluated:

1. Maximum detection range
2. Probability of detection
3. Minimum detectable radial velocity
4. Radar revisit rate
5. MTI target location accuracy
6. SAR resolution
7. SAR target location accuracy
8. Probability of false alarm
9. Electronic protection
10. MTI tracking
11. Multi-mode interleave operations
12. MTI function update times
13. Mean time between critical failure
14. Mean time to restore function
15. Maintenance demonstration
16. Failure trend data

Operational testing with Fighter Data Link equipped F-15E successfully demonstrated the ability to support ground target attack operations through both JTIDS data link and Air Battle Manager voice control. The All Service Combat Identification Evaluation Team (ASCIET) provided a robust wartime scenario to evaluate overall performance in an operationally stressful environment. The CRP test aircraft participated as an "online" intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance platform on ASCIET Day 5 using an operationally representative crew. Army CGS operators and ASCIET ground commanders were asked to compare the CRP-modified E-8C performance to the existing E-8C, which participated in all but Day 5 of the 10-day ASCIET exercise. Army and Marine users returned consistently favorable comments concerning the CRP-modified E-8C. One commander stated "...80 percent of targets successfully engaged were a direct result of [CRP] Joint STARS cueing." The CRP modification supports the war fighter's ability to execute the operational mission. Although increased system performance was not a requirement, the CRP provided an increase in efficiency and capability for both the operator and maintainer. Based on a high mean time between critical failure, low mean time to restore function, and three failure trends fixed prior to delivery, the CRP modification did not degrade Joint STARS operational suitability. Several legacy Joint STARS performance issues unrelated to CRP were observed during testing. A total of 17 deficiency reports were generated during combined DT/OT. Although important to correct, these deficiencies did not impact the overall ability of the CRP-modified E-8C to support the operational mission. These deficiencies are being investigated further and corrected during future Joint STARS testing. Since the CRP modification did not add any additional functionality, unit and theater commanders will not see any significant change in how Joint STARS will be deployed, employed, or sustained in theater. Tactics, techniques, and procedures should not change significantly.

5. LESSONS LEARNED

Lessons learned during the CRP development and test program fall into four major areas— acquisition in an open architecture, testing under schedule pressures, combined DT/OT, and scheduling test resources.

Acquisition in an Open Architecture

The acquisition community's current emphasis on open architectures with commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) elements brings with it both rewards and challenges. The experiences on the Joint STARS CRP program provide validation of these concepts but also draw attention to the need for continued innovation to gain the rewards without also falling victim to the difficulties.

The rapid pace of industry demands that developers be prepared for continuous change in commercial product lines both during development and after fielding of the system. In the CRP development program there were over a dozen product line changes that had to be accommodated. Part of this preparation demands built-in design flexibility to incorporate component changes and continued funding for cyclic upgrades necessary to avoid future obsolescence and gain the rewards of an open architecture after fielding. The gains of an open architecture are lost without the fiscal ability to continue incorporation of technology advancements.

Developers must adopt a system-level perspective vice a component perspective. CRP designed the E-8C environment (e.g. EMI) to accommodate commercial equipment by moving requirements to the system level. This increased the ability to accommodate commercial components within a military weapon system with often more stringent requirements.

Implementing requirements in software vice hardware (e.g. pulse compression unit and signal preprocessor functions moved to RASP's software) precluded the problem of component obsolescence while saving weight, power, and space on the aircraft. Such an approach was enabled by the rapidly increasing power of commercially available hardware and software. The increased computing power of components brought with it tremendous improvements in capabilities without costing more. Moving requirements into the software arena can effectively be managed through a less formal, more rapid spiral development approach characterized, in the case of CRP, by weekly software releases. This approach reduced the risk that any single change would have a significant, negative impact. Such an approach required cooperative developers and testers working side by side. Finally, creation of a common software baseline for both the air and ground segments of Joint STARS eliminated costs and schedule delays of implementing future changes into separate airborne and ground modifications.

Lesson Learned—developers must consider industry dynamics. Developers must be prepared for continuous change in the commercial product line, both during development and after fielding. Part of that preparation is continued funding for the cyclic upgrades after the design is complete. These upgrades are necessary to avoid future obsolescence and gain the advantages of an open architecture. Developers must adopt a system-level perspective vice a component perspective to ease incorporation of commercial components into a military weapon system. Implementing requirements in software vice hardware can save money and maximize expandability given ever more capable computing systems. A less formal, more rapid spiral development approach can work given effective teaming among developers and testers. Finally, a common software baseline for both the air and ground segments eases incorporation of future software changes throughout the system life cycle.

Testing Under Schedule Pressures

Rarely does a program adhere to its pre-planned schedule. Many times, the end date is fixed in time with significant milestones "slipping to the right", thereby compressing the remaining time, usually relegated to the test program. Many programs nobly attempt to be event driven, but various pressures, unforeseen at the beginning of the program, often lead them to be schedule driven. As example, long-range test assets (targets, range time, etc.) need to be scheduled two weeks in advance. A one-day program slip can ultimately result in a two-week slip simply because of conflicts in re-scheduling assets.

This scenario is commonplace in today's development environment. What was unique to the CRP program is the way in which this shortened schedule timeline was dealt with without compromising the integrity of the delivered product or impacting the effectiveness of the test program. The CRP technical review process dictated that software or hardware changes be reviewed two days prior to a test flight. Ideally, a new baseline would be established in response to these changes, and any required tests would be complete prior to a technical review board. Test results would be discussed at the review board with any resultant questions or actions being resolved prior to flying. Normally, holding the board two days before a test flight left sufficient time to resolve any issues that may have surfaced during the technical review. Occasionally CRP review boards were held the afternoon prior to a morning flight with software code still undergoing final checkout. Although this process is more prone to non-stable software impacting final results, a decision to fly was made by the program manager only after a thorough risk assessment was made. Because the CRP testing only involved the "back end" mission equipment that operates independent of the flight deck equipment, safety-of-flight was never compromised. The prime contractor, Northrop Grumman, established a software build

process whereby the software build was "rolled" weekly. This process enabled each software build to contain fewer changes, thereby reducing the risk that the changes would have a major impact on the build. While this strategy reduced the individual risk associated with each change, it increased the potential regression liability if second-order problems were discovered after the initial check out.

Lesson Learned—processes are in place for a reason. They were designed with good intentions in mind (safety and technical goals) but do not always fit nicely into today's world of increased development tempos, thereby increasing the risk associated with the program. For the CRP, risk came in the form of the following question: "What is the probability of occurrence and resultant impact of obtaining invalid test data by flying a mission before the software is fully integrated?" For the aggressive CRP schedule, driven by the requirement for cost management, each decision the program manager made was based on a thorough understanding of the associated risk. The CRP mission was successful due to the methodical spiral implementation of software functionality accompanied by rigorous lab testing.

Combined DT/OT

Normally, a military program dictates that a Contractor conducted Development Test (DT) be performed to assess compliance with the technical requirements. Once DT is concluded, the system is handed over to the user, or government test force and an Operational Test (OT), conducted by government personnel is performed to assess operational suitability of the system. The negative aspects of this approach include increased test duration, increased cost, and the lack of sharing of information/results between the system developers (Contractor) and the user (Government). Combined DT/OT strives to reduce costs and provide early feedback on the operational effectiveness and suitability of the system to the development personnel. When planning a test program, OT objectives and test needs should be identified from the beginning. Unfortunately, this was not done on the CRP; it came after contract award. Therefore, through poor planning, CRP was forced to combine OT objectives on the same missions that were being flown to measure DT objectives. This test program (Combined DT/OT) was successful, although identifying OT objectives prior to contract award would have enabled early planning of required sorties and resulted in further efficiencies.

One of the challenges to a combined DT/OT test program is determining when the OT requirements have been met. Operational test requires a final configuration. The CRP finished on the 83rd software version. Some OT objectives were signed off on software versions 60-70. Were the objectives signed off during those software versions "final"? Did changes to other objectives in higher versions affect these (previously tested) objectives (i.e. regression liability)? Through this method of conducting operational tests, the program therefore, assumed additional risk. The

CRP had two dedicated OT sorties although different software versions were flown on each. Software was "finalized" at version 83C *after* the test program ended. In the case of the CRP, these changes did not impact the formal test results.

Lesson Learned—Operational test objectives and requirements should be identified as early as possible—preferably before contract award. Further, it is advisable that at least one OT mission be flown after delivery of the *final* software version.

Scheduling Test Resources

Due to budget constraints, there is a big push to conduct more modeling & simulation in combination with ground tests and reduce the number of actual flight tests. Predicting the number of sorties a test program requires is fairly simple process. For CRP, 12 sorties were predicted with an additional 6 sorties reserved for backup. Fifteen sorties were flown to meet the combined requirements of DT and OT; which is actually 17% less than the total number of flights allocated. Predicting laboratory hours tends to be more difficult. The number of actual laboratory hours required during the CRP was more than double the predicted amount. Additionally, a few test points that were originally planned for evaluation in the laboratory were moved to the aircraft because the laboratory was unable to simulate the correct test conditions.

Lesson Learned—As more programs finish modeling & simulation and ground tests, use their data as a starting point for predicting future program's test budget.

6. CONCLUSION

The Computer Replacement Program met all its development objectives and will be fielded on the entire Joint STARS fleet. CRP has established a new baseline configuration that will make dealing with the problem of diminishing manufacturing sources easier and reduce the system's life cycle costs. Use of commercial equipment within an open architecture will facilitate future cyclic upgrades over the life of the program. The CRP modification supports the war fighter's ability to execute the operational mission with increased efficiency and capability for both the operator and maintainer. Lessons learned included applying innovative acquisition processes in an open architecture, adapting to processes while under schedule pressure, ensuring early operational tester involvement, and estimating laboratory and ground testing in addition to flight-testing.

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Captain Brian Kish is currently the E-8C System Test Division Chief for the Joint STARS Test Force. He has been with the United States Air Force for over 9 years. He has a Bachelor of Science degree in Aerospace Engineering from Illinois Institute of Technology and a Master of Science degree in Aeronautical Engineering from the Air Force Institute of Technology. Captain Kish is also a graduate of the United States Air Force Test Pilot School. He has performed research and analysis on vehicle dynamics, human operator dynamics, and aircraft handling qualities, for fixed-wing aircraft. He has authored two technical reports and six technical articles and papers. He is a member of the American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Society of Flight Test Engineers, Air Force Association, and Soaring Society of America.

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